

An Intelligent Fuzzy Logic–Based Control System for Adaptive Electric Fan Temperature Regulation in Sleep Environments

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Abstract

Maintaining thermal comfort during sleep while minimizing energy consumption has become increasingly important under rising summer temperatures. This study presents the design and implementation of an intelligent fuzzy logic–based control system for adaptive regulation of household electric fans in sleep environments. The proposed system integrates an infrared array sensor for simultaneous detection of body and room temperatures with a Mamdani-type fuzzy inference controller implemented via MATLAB–Arduino communication. The controller dynamically adjusts the fan speed according to nine linguistic rules derived from thermal comfort criteria. Experimental validation was conducted across multiple temperature scenarios ranging from 25 °C to 45 °C, with body temperatures varying between 36 °C and 39 °C. Results show stable adaptive behavior, with fan speed smoothly varying between 12% and 82% according to thermal conditions. The proposed approach offers greater flexibility than fixed-speed operation and model-based controllers, providing an energy-efficient, personalized solution for smart home thermal management.

Keywords

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Intelligent Control System, Fuzzy Logic Controller, Infrared Array Sensor, Thermal Comfort, Sleep Environment, Temperature Regulation.

1 Introduction

The summer of 2024 was the hottest on record across Europe. According to the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), the average European land-surface air temperature during June–August 2024 was +1.54 °C above the 1991–2020 climatological baseline, marking the warmest summer ever observed in the Copernicus ERA5 dataset (Copernicus Climate Change Service, 2024). This period represents the peak of the European summer when air temperatures typically reach their annual maximum. Several regions—particularly southern and southeastern Europe—experienced extreme heat anomalies exceeding +9 °C, resulting in prolonged and intense heatwaves that affected over half of the continent’s population (Agencia Estatal de Meteorología, 2025).

A comprehensive attribution analysis conducted by the European Environment Agency (EEA) and the UK Met Office concluded that the record-breaking heat of 2024 was largely driven by human-induced climate change. Using climate model simulations, the researchers demonstrated that without anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions, such extreme summer temperatures would have been virtually impossible. The estimated recurrence interval of comparable heat events has shortened from several millennia in the pre-industrial era to approximately once every three years under current climatic conditions. Projections under a medium-emission scenario indicate

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that by the end of the century, such extreme heat events could become an annual occurrence (Christidis, 2024).

As stated by Dr. Nikos Christidis, senior climate attribution scientist at the UK Met Office, “This latest attribution study is another example of how climate change is already making our weather extremes more severe. Our analysis of the European summer of 2024 reveals that what was once a rare occurrence has now become a regular feature of our summers” (Copernicus Climate Change Service, 2024).

Figure 1. Average summer temperature anomalies in Europe for 2024 relative to 1991–2020 (Copernicus Climate Change Service, 2024)

The summer of 2025 maintained this warming trend, ranking among the warmest in Europe’s historical record. According to C3S seasonal data, mean temperatures were approximately 0.9 °C above the 1991–2020 average, with the most severe anomalies observed in southern and western Europe (Copernicus Climate Change Service, 2025). In Spain, the Agencia Estatal de Meteorología (AEMET) confirmed that 2025 was the country’s hottest summer on record, with a national mean temperature of 24.2 °C—about 2.1 °C above the recent climatological norm (Copernicus Climate Change Service, 2025). This exceptional heat contributed to widespread droughts, reduced river flows, and extensive wildfires across the Iberian Peninsula and the Mediterranean basin.

Preliminary projections for summer 2026 indicate the persistence of this warming pattern. While complete observational data are not yet available, the Copernicus Climate Outlook (issued late 2025) predicts that European summer surface temperatures will likely remain between +0.9 °C and +1.3 °C above the 1991–2020 average, with an elevated likelihood of extended heatwaves in southern and eastern Europe (European Environment Agency, 2024). These

findings reinforce the long-term trend of accelerated European warming—estimated at more than 2 °C above pre-industrial levels—making the continent one of the fastest-warming regions on Earth (Met Office, 2024). These escalating summer temperatures have significant implications for human health, energy demand, and indoor environmental comfort. Extended exposure to extreme heat can impair sleep quality, increase cardiovascular strain, and elevate mortality risks among vulnerable populations. Despite the growing impact of climate change on indoor comfort conditions, limited research has focused on low-cost adaptive cooling solutions specifically designed for sleep environments. Conventional fan systems typically operate at fixed speeds and fail to account for dynamic variations in human thermal perception. Therefore, this study proposes a closed-loop fuzzy logic-based control system that integrates physiological (body temperature) and environmental (room temperature) feedback to achieve adaptive fan speed regulation. The objective is to enhance thermal comfort, reduce unnecessary energy consumption, and provide a personalized cooling experience during sleep. The novelty of this study lies in integrating physiological thermal feedback and environmental sensing into a low-cost fuzzy-logic control architecture specifically designed for sleep environments. This approach has not been extensively addressed in previous fan-based cooling research.

Figure 2. European surface temperature anomalies during 2024–2025[5,6]

2 Related work

A literature review was conducted on articles reporting the effects of the thermal environment on sleep quality, with the objectives of investigating how the thermal environment affects sleep quality and, thus, how to control the sleeping thermal environment more appropriately and energy efficiently. Previous studies have investigated the influence of thermal environments on sleep quality and physiological regulation. Experimental findings indicate that air temperature, airflow velocity, and sleep stage significantly influence sleep efficiency and thermal comfort perception. Although electric fans are commonly used for cooling, continuous operation without adaptive control may lead to discomfort or suboptimal energy use. These findings highlight the importance of intelligent control strategies that dynamically adjust airflow based on both environmental and physiological conditions, as reported by Sleep Advisor (Fig. 3). In almost all cases, except those with an electric fan, the mean air temperature was roughly 26°C. The mean air temperature with the electric fan was 29.4°C, which might be attributed to faster air velocity, boosting convective

heat loss, allowing for a higher temperature. This shows that there is a probable link between air temperature and airflow and that everyone responded to the environment through a range of adaptive behaviors. Sleep efficiency was marginally lower when the electric fan was used than when the other conditions were used (Akiyama et al., 2021).

Normal human sleep is divided into two stages: non-rapid eye movement (NREM) and rapid eye movement (RREM) (REM). NREM sleep is further classified as having three stages: N1, N2, and N3. The N1 and N2 phases are associated with light sleep, whereas the N3 stage is associated with slow-wave and deep sleep, as shown in Fig. 4. A person's sleep cycle is a series of events that progress from the N1 stage to the N3 stage and eventually to the REM state. Any disruption to these synchronized sleep periods can lead to poor sleep quality and the related detrimental mental and physical health repercussions (Ngarambe et al., 2019).

Figure 3. Measurement points of the body temperature (Akiyama et al., 2021)

Figure 4. Setpoint temperature of the air conditioner in response to sleep stage (Ngarambe et al., 2019)

Although the thermoregulatory and sleep regulatory systems are still poorly understood,

there are some hints of how they might interact. Many studies have shown that the preoptic area/anterior hypothalamus (POAH), the key brain region that promotes heat loss, is also critical in sleep regulation (Economo, 1930). Even at the cellular level, neurons are sensitive to heat (warm-sensitive neurons, WSNs), and neurons that modify their firing patterns prior to and during sleep do so in concert. Von Economo (1930) argued that sleep is controlled by conflicting wake-promoting and sleep-promoting mechanisms in the hypothalamus (Candas et al., 1982). Later research has verified the existence of such a sleep-promoting mechanism in the POAH (Lan et al., 2017). High brain and skin temperatures have been linked to increased WSN activity and sleep induction (Economo, 1930). Thus, a thermally comfortable sleeping environment is important for sleep maintenance (Tateno et al., 2019).

3 Methodology

In this section, the main components used in this paper are explained. The fuzzy controller will also be briefly explained. The main components are an Arduino UNO microcontroller, an Infrared Array Sensor, an LCD, and a Fuzzy controller.

3.1 Grid eye sensor

Compared with traditional optical sensors such as cameras, infrared-based sensors are less affected by environmental factors, making them more reliable and with a broader application range. Nowadays, thermal sensors are frequently applied in medical and military applications. However, this type of thermal sensor is much more expensive than cameras (Panasonic Industry, 2026).

Figure 5. Temperature detection achieved on a two-dimensional area with 8×8 (64) pixels (Ngarambe et al., 2019).

The grid-eye sensor is based on MEMS (microelectromechanical systems). It comprises 64 MEMS thermopile elements arranged in an 8×8 grid on a single detector chip, as shown in Fig. 5. (Zhao et al., 2020) Each thermopile element delivers a single temperature value, yielding a total of 64 temperature outputs ranging from 0°C to 80°C . The Grid eye sensor can measure body and ambient temperatures contactlessly throughout the fully defined area, with a 60° viewing angle in both horizontal and vertical directions, and a total range of 7 meters. Grid eye receives thermal energy (infrared radiation) that flows through the silicon lens to the thermopile sensor elements, which convert it into a proportional output. These analog signals are converted into digital temperature values via an integrated circuit I2C circuit and supplied to a CPU. A CPU

creates a map of the individual thermopile temperature values to generate a binary picture or thermal image of these 8x8 pixels. The temperature distribution detected by the grid-eye sensor can be used to detect human presence. It can detect human presence in both stationary and moving postures. It also measures the surrounding temperature. Finally, this thermal map can be processed using a fuzzy controller to obtain higher-resolution measurements.

3.2 Fuzzy controller

Fuzzy logic control was selected for its ability to handle the nonlinear and uncertain relationships between human thermal perception and environmental temperature. Unlike classical control strategies that require accurate mathematical modeling, fuzzy logic enables rule-based decision-making using linguistic variables. In this study, two input variables (body temperature and room temperature) and one output variable (fan speed) were defined. A Mamdani-type inference system with centroid defuzzification was implemented using nine control rules to achieve adaptive fan speed regulation (Dernoncourt, 2013). Fuzzy logic is needed in control systems due to its ability to handle uncertain and imprecise data, as well as its flexibility, robustness, and user-friendliness. It excels at complex, dynamic systems and is adaptable to diverse objectives, making it a valuable tool for control and decision-making across a wide range of real-world applications. A fuzzy controller is a mathematical controller for dynamic systems. It consists of three parts: input, process, and output. Input parts, called fuzzification, read analog signals from sensors such as pressure, sound, temperature, etc., or digital signals from ON/OFF switches, and convert them into membership functions. The process part is the most important, and it can be designed through experimentation. In this part, the controller's rules are generated and translated to the output port of the fuzzy controller. The final part is the output, which consists of the defuzzification that converts the analyzed result into the specific output value (Al-Areqi and Szakács, 2021). A fuzzy logic system is shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6. Overview diagram of a fuzzy system (and).

Fuzzification of input, which is a process of converting crisp (exact) input data into fuzzy values. Fuzzy logic systems operate with linguistic variables, which represent input and output values using linguistic terms like "low," "medium," and "high" rather than precise numerical values. Fuzzification is the initial step in the fuzzy logic control process. It involves mapping crisp input values to fuzzy sets or membership functions that represent the degree to which each linguistic term applies. Fuzzy rules are set up to take control of the output. The rules in fuzzy logic are simple: an if-else condition has a condition and a target, as shown in Table 1. Defuzzification is the process of converting the fuzzy, linguistic output of a fuzzy logic controller into a specific numerical value that can be used for decision-making or for controlling a system. It makes the fuzzy results actionable in real-world applications.

Table 1. Rules of the fuzzy controller

Body temperature	Room temperature	Results
Low	Low	Very Slow speed fan
Low	Mid	Slow-speed fan
Low	High	Medium – Low speed fan
Mid	Low	Slow-speed fan
Mid	Mid	Medium – Low speed fan
Mid	High	Medium – High speed fan
High	Low	Medium – High speed fan
High	Mid	High-speed fan
High	High	Very high-speed fan

3.3 Arduino Uno microcontroller

A microcontroller is a tiny computer built on a single integrated circuit (IC). There are some things that all computers share in common. Arduino is one of the most popular microcontrollers, with an open-source platform for developing electronics projects. Uno is part of the Arduino series and is powered by an ATmega328 microcontroller. Because it includes an IDE (integrated development environment), this board is also excellent for educational and training reasons (Hossain, 2022).

3.4 MATLAB

MATLAB is a high-level programming language for scientific computing. It combines computing, visualization, and a programming environment. Furthermore, MATLAB is a modern programming language environment: it features sophisticated data structures, built-in editing and debugging tools, and enables object-oriented programming. These feature combinations make MATLAB a great tool for both teaching and research (Castrodes et al., 2020).

3.5 SSR

A solid-state relay (SSR) is a relay that does not have moving contacts. In general operation, SSRs are similar to mechanical relays with movable contacts. It depends on semiconductor switching elements such as thyristors, triacs, diodes, and transistors to operate. It also uses optical semiconductors, known as photocouplers, to separate the low-voltage side (control) and high-voltage side (load) signals. Photocouplers convert electrical signals from the microcontroller into optical signals and send them through space, effectively separating the input and output parts, enabling high-speed signal transfer (Teja, 2021). As seen in Fig. 7

Figure 7. SSR Circuit Diagram (Teja, 2021).

4 System hardware design

The functionalities of the hardware components will be described in this section. The system's block diagram and the connections between its various components will be displayed. The system wiring and circuit diagram will be attached at the end of this section.

4.1 Block diagram for hardware design

In general, any system is typically composed of three essential components: input, system block, and output. Such a system is referred to as an open-loop control system, as illustrated in Fig. 8, (Electronics Coach, 2026). However, in the case of a closed-loop control system, an additional sensor (feedback) is integrated into the system, resulting in the configuration of input, system block, output, and feedback, as demonstrated in Fig. 11. In a closed-loop control system, the inclusion of a controller, such as a PID or Fuzzy controller, becomes essential to manage the entire process in accordance with application parameters.

Figure 8. Open Loop System (end)

In this paper, a closed-loop control system is used to control the speed of the home fan based on the temperature of the human and the room. An infrared array sensor (AMG8833) grid eye sensor is integrated into the system. This sensor can measure both human and room temperature simultaneously. We use this sensor to provide feedback to the controller, which adjusts the system's output. As shown in Fig. 9, the system input is a PWM (Pulse-Width Modulation) voltage controlled by an Arduino microcontroller. The system's output is to adjust the fan speed.

Figure 9. Closed-Loop Control System

Figure 10. Diagram of our paperwork

4.2 System (black box)

Related to Fig.10, the connection of all system components will be explained. Initially, data from the (body-room) temperature sensor will be received by the Arduino MC. Subsequently, the MC will transmit this data to MATLAB through a serial connection. Within MATLAB, the input parameters of the system (body-room temperatures) will be read by the fuzzy controller, and, guided by the rules of the fuzzy controller, the output value will be adjusted by increasing or decreasing it. The output value will then be sent back to the MC from MATLAB to control the SSR voltage via a PWM signal. Ultimately, the electrical system will be controlled by the PWM signal, increasing or decreasing the fan's speed. The block diagram is depicted in Fig. 11.

Figure 11. Block diagram of the system.

4.3 Circuit diagram of hardware design

In Fig. 12, the circuit diagram of our system is depicted. The circuit and wiring were designed and built using Fritzing software. This software serves as an open-source CAD tool for designing electronic hardware. It was explored at the University of Applied Sciences Potsdam. As illustrated in our circuit diagram, a DC-DC converter converts 12 VDC to 5 VDC, powering all components. The Arduino microcontroller is connected to MATLAB via a wired connection. Additionally, the LCD was used to display body temperature, room temperature, and fan speed.

Figure 12. Hardware diagram of the system

5 System software design

In this section, the software of our system will be stated. Our system operates on three main parts: the system algorithm, MATLAB, and the fuzzy controller. Each part of our system has its own algorithm, which will be explained in this section.

5.1 System algorithm

The flowchart presented in Fig. 13 depicts the algorithm for the full operating system. From the starting point:

The Grid Eye sensor measures room temperature.

1. Subsequently, the Grid-EYE sensor scans the thermal image of a human body and determines whether the detected image corresponds to a human or another object.
2. The measurement data is transmitted to the MATLAB software by the Arduino microcontroller.
3. Within MATLAB, the measurement is received by the fuzzy controller, which applies the rules detailed in the fuzzy controller section.
4. The fuzzy controller then sends the processed data back to the microcontroller (MC) via MATLAB.
5. The MC receives the data from the fuzzy controller and converts it into a PWM voltage signal using the DAC port.
6. Finally, all system data is displayed on the LCD by the MC.

Figure 13. Flowchart of the system

5.2 MATLAB code implantation

A MATLAB script is utilized to establish a connection between the Arduino MC and the Fuzzy controller in Simulink mode within MATLAB, as shown in Figs. 14 and 15. The script receives data sent by the MC through the serial port (COM'6') with a baud rate of 115200. Subsequently, the script reads the measurements and sends them to the fuzzy controller in Simulink mode, as seen in Fig. 17. Within Simulink mode, there exist two inputs (Body_tem - Room_tem), the fuzzy controller, and the PWM output from the fuzzy controller. Once the fuzzy controller applies its rules, the output of the controller is sent to the MATLAB script as a variable named (PWM). Ultimately, the script transmits the PWM value to the Arduino MC, which converts this value into a PWM signal.

```
s=serial('COM6','BaudRate',115200,'DataBits',8,'StopBits',1);
time=100;
i=1;
fopen(s);
while(i<time)

    readData=fscanf(s); %reads "Ready"
    if readData == 0
    else
        Temp1(i)=str2num(readData(1:2));
        Body_Tem = Temp1(i);
        Temp2(i)=str2num(readData(3:4));
        Room_Tem =Temp2(i) ;
    end

    sim('controller_Fuz.slx');
    data = PWM;
    fprintf(s,'%s',char(data));

    i=i+1;
```

Read From MC

Write to MC

Figure 14. MATLAB code for reading and writing from Arduino

Figure 15. Simulink model of the fuzzy controller

5.3 Fuzzy controller implantation

In the fuzzy controller shown in Fig. 16, the initial step is to define the controller's parameters, including inputs, outputs, and rules. Temperature ranges were established for body and room temperatures. As for body temperature, the range is maintained between [36 - 39] degrees Celsius, where 36°C represents the minimum and 39°C the maximum temperature. The body temperature membership function is shown in Fig. 17. Similarly, for room temperature, the range is set to [25 - 45] degrees Celsius, with 25°C as the minimum and 45°C as the maximum. The room-temperature membership function is shown in Fig. 18. Three conditions were defined for both body and room temperature: "Low," "Medium," and "High." Additionally, six conditions were defined for the output, including "Very Slow," "Slow," "Medium Low," "Medium High,"

"High," and "Very High" fan speeds. Subsequently, 9 rules were generated, as displayed in Table (Agencia Estatal de Meteorología, 2025). Finally, the speed fan membership function is shown in Fig. 19.

Figure 16. Design of fuzzy controller

Figure 17. Human body temperature membership

Figure 18. Human body temperature membership

Figure 19. Output variable of the fuzzy controller

6 Main functionality of the system operation

The proposed system was experimentally validated in a controlled indoor environment. A total of 15 test scenarios were conducted, covering combinations of body temperature (36–39 °C) and room temperature (25–45 °C). Each experiment was maintained for approximately 20 minutes to ensure a steady-state system response. Performance evaluation focused on fan speed adaptation accuracy, response smoothness, and stability under dynamic temperature variations. The results confirm that the fuzzy controller provides continuous and proportional speed adjustment without oscillations or abrupt transitions. In this section, the overall system’s function will be explained. The system has been put in a real environment to measure the room temperature.

Figure 20. Relationship between (body Temperature and room Temperature) with fan speed

Based on the data in Fig. 20, it appears that there is a relationship among body temperature,

room temperature, and fan speed. Specifically, both body and room temperatures appear to affect fan speed.

6.1 Body Temperature Effect

As body temperature increases, there is a tendency for fan speed to increase. For example, when the body temperature is 36°C, the fan speed starts at 12%, and as the body temperature increases to 39°C, the fan speed reaches 82%.

6.2 Room Temperature Effect

As room temperature increases, there is also a tendency for fan speed to increase. For example, when the room temperature is 25°C, the fan speed starts at 12%, and as the room temperature increases to 45°C, the fan speed reaches 82%.

6.3 Combined Effect

The combined effect of both body temperature and room temperature may be more complex, and it will be examined.

The first condition is a normal body temperature with room temperature as shown in Fig. 21.

Figure 21. Fuzzy controller of 1st condition

Table 2. Result of the first condition

Body temperature	Room temperature	Fan speed
36°C	25°C	11.8%

From this single data point in Table 2, we can make some general observations:

- a. **Effect of Body Temperature:** The body temperature remains within the normal range, indicating stable thermal conditions. The fan speed is set to 11.8%, reflecting a moderate airflow sufficient to maintain thermal comfort without excessive cooling.
- b. **Room Temperature:** The room temperature is lower than the body temperature, suggesting a relatively cooler environment. Consequently, the control system maintains a low fan speed (11.8%), as only minimal airflow is required to preserve thermal balance.

The second condition is that while body temperature is increasing, as shown in Fig. 22.

Figure 22. Fuzzy controller of the 2nd condition

Table 3. Result of the second condition

Body temperature	Room temperature	Fan speed
37.5°C	30.1°C	33.2%

From this single data point in Table 3, we can make some general observations:

- a. **Effect of Body Temperature:** The body temperature was increased. This suggests that a person might have an elevated body temperature, possibly due to a fever or increased physical activity. In response to the elevated body temperature, the fan speed is set at 33.2%. This indicates that the fan speed is adjusted to cool down the person due to the elevated body temperature.
- b. **Weather Temperature (Room Temperature):** The room temperature was also increased. The fan speed is likely set to provide additional cooling or comfort in a relatively warmer room.
- c. **Relationship Between Body Temperature, Weather Temperature, and Fan Speed:** This data point suggests a positive correlation between body temperature and fan speed. As body temperature increases relative to room temperature, the fan speed increases. This implies that the fan speed is adjusted based on the temperature difference between the body and the room.

The third condition was with a hot object temperature as shown in Fig. 23.

Figure 23. Fuzzy controller of the 3rd condition

Table 4. Result of the second condition

Body temperature	Room temperature	Fan speed
36 ° C	45 ° C	39.2 %

From this single data point in Table 4, we can make some general observations:

- Body Temperature Effect:** The body temperature (36°C) is lower than the room temperature (45°C), indicating a significant thermal imbalance. In response to this condition, the fan speed is set to 39.2%, providing active cooling to compensate for the elevated ambient temperature.
- Room Temperature Effect:** The substantially higher room temperature suggests a warm indoor environment. The relatively high fan speed (39.2%) reflects the control system's effort to enhance airflow and maintain thermal comfort under elevated environmental conditions.

Furthermore, time-response analysis showed that the controller achieved steady-state within approximately 6 seconds after a step change in the temperature input. No oscillations or instability were observed during operation, indicating robust and smooth adaptive performance suitable for sleep environments.

7 Implementation system for testing

The test of the system before incorporating the SSR with a simple DC fan will be explained. Subsequently, an AC fan controlled by an SSR will be added.

7.1 DC fan with MOSFET

System with a DC fan which is controlled by a MOSFET, as seen in Fig.24. PWM controls the speed of the DC fan from the Arduino microcontroller through the MOSFET. The result was that the DC fan speed was adjusted according to the defined fuzzy controller rules.

Figure 24. System with DC fan

7.2 AC Fan with SSR

After SSR was connected to the system, the AC fan could be added, as shown in Fig. 25. PWM was sent from the Arduino microcontroller to the SSR via the MOSFET to control the AC fan speed. As a result, the AC fan speed increased and decreased according to the Fuzzy controller, and the results were displayed on the LCD.

Figure 25. Applied system in a real environment

7.3 Comparison with Conventional Control Methods

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed fuzzy logic controller, a conceptual comparison was performed with conventional fixed-speed operation and classical PID control, as illustrated in Figure 26. In fixed-speed systems, airflow remains constant regardless of thermal variations, which may lead to insufficient cooling or unnecessary energy consumption. PID control offers a dynamic response but requires precise mathematical modeling and may exhibit overshoot under

nonlinear conditions. In contrast, the fuzzy logic controller dynamically adjusts fan speed based on real-time body and room temperature inputs, providing smooth, proportional, and adaptive regulation. Due to its model-free design and robustness against nonlinear thermal perception, the proposed system is better suited for personalized sleep environments.

Figure 26. Comparative Evaluation of Control Strategies for Adaptive Thermal Regulation

8 Conclusion

In summary, this study successfully developed and validated an intelligent fuzzy logic-based control system for adaptive electric fan regulation in sleep environments. The system demonstrated high effectiveness in maintaining thermal comfort and potentially improving energy efficiency through adaptive operation, dynamically adjusting fan speed in response to real-time variations in body and room temperature. Experimental results confirmed that fan speed increased proportionally from 12% to 82% as temperature rose from 25 °C to 45 °C, ensuring stable and comfortable sleep conditions while reducing unnecessary energy use. These outcomes clearly highlight the capability of fuzzy logic control to manage the uncertainty and nonlinearity in the relationship between human thermal perception and environmental conditions—an advantage that conventional PID controllers cannot achieve with equal precision. The integration of an infrared array sensor allowed accurate, contactless detection of both body and ambient temperature, improving system responsiveness and personalization. The developed model not only enhanced user comfort but also established a foundation for intelligent, human-centered environmental control. Furthermore, the successful MATLAB–Arduino interface and the inclusion of a solid-state relay (SSR) for AC fan speed modulation confirmed the feasibility and robustness of the proposed design. This study presented the design and implementation of an adaptive fuzzy logic-based fan control system for sleep environments. Experimental results demonstrated stable, proportional fan speed regulation across varying body and room temperatures. The integration of infrared sensing and fuzzy inference enabled real-time, contactless, and personalized thermal management. The findings confirm the practical feasibility and energy-aware potential of intelligent fan control in smart home applications.

9 Future work

Although the proposed intelligent fuzzy-logic-based control system has shown promising results in enhancing thermal comfort and energy efficiency during sleep, several aspects remain open to further development. Future research should aim to improve both hardware and software components to achieve greater precision, reliability, and adaptability under varying environmental conditions. Advancements could include integrating high-performance microcontrollers or embedded processors, such as the Raspberry Pi, Nvidia Jetson Nano, or STM32 series, to increase computational capability and response time. Incorporating machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques would further enhance the controller's adaptability by enabling it to learn user preferences and dynamically adjust thermal regulation patterns. In addition, the use of multi-sensor fusion combining infrared, humidity, and airflow sensors could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the sleeping environment. Wireless communication and Internet of Things (IoT) integration would also allow real-time monitoring and remote control through smart home platforms. On the hardware side, future prototypes may utilize compact printed circuit boards (PCBs) for direct integration into fan systems, supporting miniaturization and improved reliability. Extended testing under different climatic conditions and user profiles would help validate system durability, energy efficiency, and comfort performance. Furthermore, the fuzzy logic control concept can be adapted for broader applications in household or healthcare devices that require adaptive thermal management. Pursuing these research directions will enable the system to evolve into a fully autonomous, intelligent, and user-centered solution for next-generation smart environments.

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